

**APPLICATION OF COBB-DOUGLAS PRODUCTION FUNCTION IN
AGRICULTURE: A CASE STUDY OF SMALLHOLDER PLANTAIN FARMS
IN EBONYI STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract. *Cobb-Douglas production function was widely used in manufacturing, economics and productivity studies across many sectors. Here, it was applied in agriculture to study smallholder plantain farms in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Data were collected using a well-structured questionnaire from sixty (60) smallholder plantain farmers randomly selected from the three zones of the study area using multistage and random sampling techniques. Data collected were statistically analyzed. Results showed that smallholder plantain farmers in the area had mean age of 39.67 years, with mean household size of 9 persons, 15 years of experience in farming and mean farm size of 0.675 hectares of land. The R^2 value of 0.6924 implied that over sixty-nine percent (69%) of the fluctuations in the yields of plantain was accounted for by the explanatory variables included in the model. The F -ratio of 45.044 which was significant at 1% showed that the coefficients of the explanatory variables were statistically different from zero and the Durbin Watson value of 1.798 implied the absence of autocorrelation in the model hence its goodness of fit. Capital resources (0.034) and planting material (0.084) were statistically and*

positively significant at 1%. Labour (0.067) and farm size (0.017) were also positively related to plantain output at 5% level of significance. Cost of agrochemical (-0.084) was negatively related to plantain output at 5% level significance. Finally, fertilizer (-0.081) was insignificant and negatively related to plantain output in the area. Return to scale was (0.037) which implied increasing return to scale for smallholder plantain farmers in the study area. Also the most technical efficient factor inputs were land (8.722), labour (3.355), agrochemical (2.134), fertilizer and capital resources with the values of 1.952 and 1.885 respectively. The least technically efficient factor is planting material (0.234). Capital resource (96.15) was underutilized. Planting material (0.0148), labour (0.09612) and farm size (land) (0.0445) were over-utilized. Fertilizer (-0.0678) and agrochemical (-0.084) were extremely over-utilized. Farmers in the study area pay less attention in plantain production. Cobb-Douglas production function is strongly recommended for productivity studies as it X-rays what is obtainable in a particular study area.

Keywords: *Cobb-Douglas, Smallholder, Plantain, Farms, Ebonyi*

Introduction. Plantain is an important staple and source of income for the smallholder farmers who grow the crop in the humid forest and mid-altitude agroecologies of sub-Saharan Africa (Njukwe, Tenkouano, and Amah, 2008). Today plantain is grown in 52 countries with world production of 33 million metric tons (FAO, 2004). Production of plantain in Nigeria from 1990 to 2004 indicates a downward trend in terms of yield per hectare while price per ton have steadily increased within the period (FAO, 2006, FAO STAT, 2011). However, only eight African Countries were named among the top ten world producers of plantain with Nigeria ranking as the fifth highest producer of the crop (FAO, 2004). In terms of total production, the banana ranks after oranges, grapes, and apples, but when plantain production is added, it becomes the world's number one fruit crop (Kainga and Seiyabo, 2012). The phenomenon of crop productivity and growth to a large extent hinges on the input-output relationship. Plantain is one of the most important

staple food crops grown in the tropics and sub-tropics of the world. Frison and Sharrock, (1999) observed that banana and plantain represent more than 25 percent of the food energy requirement of Africa. Plantain plays vital roles in the feeding systems of both human beings and farm animals. It has a very high nutritional value in source of dietary carbohydrates, vitamins and minerals. Plantains are extremely rich in vitamin A. Most plantains are produced by small scale farmers who often do not have the financial resources for sustained production by means of the application of chemical fertilizers, fungicides and pesticides. Farmers attached little premium to the foregoing, and thus apply less, with the belief that plantain can always produce for itself with little organic manure derived from kitchen and animal remains (Kainga and Seiyabo, 2012). These farmers especially in Ebonyi State usually depend on natural regeneration of plants for the supply of planting materials. This is a very slow process that often produces small numbers of planting materials that are usually contaminated by various soil-borne pathogens such as nematodes. Transplanting of the contaminated materials often spreads nematodes and shortens the lifetime of plantations to only one or two cycles of cultivation, beyond which lodging occurs. Ebonyi state has no comparative advantage for plantain production but having seen several smallholder farmers producing the crop in the comfort of their homes-backyards/home gardens, got my attention, thus compelling me to ascertain the resource-use efficiency and return to scale in the smallholder plantain farms using Cobb-Douglas production function.

Cobb-Douglas production function is widely used in economics and productivity studies across many sectors, agricultural sector inclusive (Ashkan, 2012). In general, a production function is a specification of how the quantity of output behaves as a function of inputs used in production. The concept can be applied at the level of individual firms, industries, or entire economics. Since we are doing macroeconomics, we will be considering an aggregate production function, applying at the economy-wide level. Various specific mathematical forms have been put forward for the production function, but the most commonly used is that developed

by Charles Cobb and Paul Douglas in the second quarter of the 20th century (Cobb and Douglas, 1928). Here is their specification:

$$Y=AK^aL^{1-a} \quad 0<a<1 \text{-----}(1)$$

Here, Y = Aggregate output, K = Capital input, and L = Labour input. The value of A reflects the state of technology as well as the skill and education level of the workforce. *Ceteris paribus*, we would expect A to be gradually increasing.

Cobb-Douglas production function's quantitative modelling of resource inputs and production output is appealing to the research domain of agriculture. It defines the portion of land, labour, and materials needed based on the production rate, provides a much-needed piece to arriving at Inputs-Output relationships, Marginal physical product (MPP), Marginal value product (MVP), Resource-use efficiency index and Return to scale in agricultural production. It considers land, labour, cost of agrochemicals, planting materials etc. as its parameters.

Cobb-Douglas has been widely used in research on economics (Dennis *et al*, 2010), technology progress (Sircar and Choi, 2009), Climate change (Utobo, *et al*, 2016), (Banker and Natarajan, 2008; Pendharker *et al*, 2008), thus:

$$Y = Y=AK^aL^b \text{-----}(2)$$

Where: Q = Production rate; L = Labour; K = Capital/equipment; A = Technology; a and b are the output elasticity of labour and capital respectively.

Goskel and Ozden (2007) have applied the total factor productivity (TFP) with Cobb-Douglas production function in agriculture to analyze the agricultural productivity in Turkey. Cobb-Douglas production function has frequently been used in the analysis of agricultural production process. It was initially used for manufacturing industry in USA by H. Douglas and C.W. Cobb (Semasinghe, 1998). Cobb-Douglas production has the advantage of permitting hypothesis testing and calculation of confidence intervals to test the reliability of the estimates. It clearly measures the marginal contribution of each input to aggregate agricultural output, though, it requires more data than other functions, hence, a disadvantage.

The Cobb-Douglas production function (Cobb and Douglas, 1928) which will be employed in this analysis is widely used to represent the relationship between inputs and output i.e input-output relationship. The coefficients of Cobb-Douglas production function will be used to determine return to scale and resource-use efficiency in smallholder plantain farms in the area.

Methodology. The study was conducted in Ebonyi State. The State is located in the South-East part of Nigeria. It lies approximately 7°3N and longitudes 5° 4E and 6° 45E. Ebonyi State is bounded in the East by Cross River State, in the North by Benue State, in the West by Enugu state, and in the south by Abia state (EBOMOI, 2005). The State is made up of thirteen (13) Local Government Areas which constitute three (3) agricultural zones, namely: Ebonyi North, Ebonyi Central and Ebonyi South. The total land mass of the State is approximately 5,932 square kilometers.

Agriculture is the major backbone of the economy. Petty trading, blacksmithing, pottery and weaving are some of the non-farm activities prevalent in the State. Industries are found in the State and it includes the well-known Abakaliki rice milling industry, the fertilizer blending plant and the building materials industry. Large deposits of solid mineral resources such as lead, gypsum, limestone, marble stone and common salt are common in Ebonyi State and the popular crush rock (EBOMOI, 2005). The vegetation is a mixture of savanna and semi-tropical rainforest. The vegetation of the State predisposes the State to growing of different crops which include: rice, yam, cassava, cocoyam, groundnut, cowpea and vegetables. Extensive system of rearing livestock is predominant with fish farming being exceptionally predominant in the south zone of the State.

NPC, (2006), reported that Ebonyi State has a population of 2.1 million people.

Figure 1. Map of Ebonyi State

Sampling Technique. A multistage and random Sampling techniques was adopted for this study. Ebonyi State is made of 3 agricultural zones which include Ebonyi North, Central and South zones. These zones altogether are made of 13 Local Government Areas which were spread thus: Ebonyi North has four (4) Local Government Areas, namely: Izzi, Abakaliki, Ebonyi and Ohaukwu; Ebonyi Central has four (4) Local Government Areas to include Ikwo, Ezza South, Ezza North and Ishielu; Ebonyi South has five (5) Local Government Areas, they are; Ivo, Ohazara, Onicha, Afikpo South and Afikpo North.

Stage1: Two Local Government Areas were randomly selected from each agricultural zone of the State making it six (6) Local Government Areas

Stage2: Two (2) farming communities were randomly selected from each of the six (6) Local Government Areas to give twelve (12) farming communities.

Stage3: One (1) village was randomly selected from each of the twelve farming communities to give twelve (12) villages.

Stage4: Five (5) smallholder plantain farmers were randomly selected from each of the twelve (12) villages to give sixty (60) smallholder plantain farmers selected for the study.

Model Specification. Marginal value product (MVP) and the marginal factor cost for inputs at geometric mean level was derived from a Cobb-Douglas production function analysis.

$$\ln Y_i = \ln b_0 + b_1 \ln X_{1i} + b_2 \ln X_{2i} + b_3 \ln X_{3i} + b_4 \ln X_{4i} + b_5 \ln X_{5i} + b_6 \ln X_{6i} + \epsilon_i \quad (3)$$

Where: Y = total output of plantain/banana (kilogram)

X_1 = capital resources (₦)

X_2 = farm size (ha)

X_3 = labour (mandays)

X_4 = agro-chemicals (₦)

X_5 = planting material (₦)

X_6 = quantity of fertilizer applied (Kg)

Ln = natural logarithm

$B_0 - b_6$ = Co-efficients of Cobb-Douglas production function

ϵ_i = composite error term

The marginal value product (MVP) was computed as follows:

$$MVP = B_i Y_i P_Y / X_i \quad (4)$$

Where: MVP = marginal value product

B_i = Cobb-Douglas coefficient of input X_i

Y_i = geometric mean of plantain output

X_i = geometric mean of input X_i (e.g farm size in hectares)

P_y = unit price of plantain per bunch

Efficiency was measured on the basis that X_i is used efficiently if the MVP=MFC ratio is one or unity.

Decision rule:

If the ratio is less than one, it implies that X_i has been excessively used (over-utilized). If the ratio is greater than one, it implies that X_i has been underutilized.

Results and discussion

Table 1: Socioeconomic Characteristics of Smallholder Plantain Farmers in Ebonyi State

Socioeconomic Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Age (Years)			40
<20	1	1.67	
20-29	7	11.67	
30-39	12	20.00	
40-49	14	23.33	
50-59	10	16.67	
≥60	16	26.67	
Sex			
Male	22	36.67	
Female	38	63.33	
Marital Status			
Single	4	6.67	
Married	56	93.33	
Household Size			
<5	18	30	9
5-8	38	63.67	
9-12	3	5	
>12	1	1.67	
Farm Size (Ha)			
<0.5	52		0.675
0.5-0.6	6		
0.7-0.8	1		
≥0.9	1		
Educational Level			
No formal education	3	5.00	
Primary education	13	21.67	
Secondary education	24	40.00	
Tertiary education	20	33.33	

Farming Experience

<5	3	5.00	15.25
5-10	17	28.33	
11-15	13	21.67	
16-20	5	3.00	
21-25	6	10.00	
>25	14	23.33	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Table 1 showed that smallholder plantain farmers in the area had mean age of 40 years, which implied that smallholder plantain farmers were within the active and innovative working age. This finding agrees with Onyebinama (2004) who reported the productive capacity of farmers to be age determinant. Majority (63.33%) of the farmers were female and few 36.67% were male. This finding links plantain production in the study area to home garden crops as women were more in home garden activities in Ebonyi State. Majority (93.33%) of smallholder plantain farmers were married men and women. This agreed with Azeez *et al* (2015) that married men and women were more in agriculture to feed their growing families. Moreso, smallholder plantain farmers in the area had mean household size of 9 persons which agreed with Udoh and Oluwatoyin (2006), that majority average household size in Nigeria ranges from 5-8 persons. Majority (40) had up to secondary education. Also, smallholder plantain farmers had mean farming experience of 15.25 years, which agreed with Onubuogu (2013) that years of farming experience of a farmer would boost the skills of the farmer and a better understanding of the risk associated to farming. The mean farm size of 0.675 hectares of land shows that plantain production was in scale basis in the area. This agrees with Idachaba (1993), that farmers cultivating less than 3 hectares of land are smallholders and this research was geared towards smallholder plantain farms.

Table 2: Cobb-Douglas Production Function of Smallholder Plantain Farms in the area

Explanatory Variables	Coefficients	t-value
Capital resources (₦)	0.034***	3.388
Cost of planting material (₦)	0.084***	2.740
Labour (man-days)	0.067**	2.913
Cost of fertilizer (₦)	-0.081 ^{NS}	-1.147
Farm size (Ha)	0.017**	3.155
Cost of Agrochemical (₦)	-0.084**	-2.663
Constant	75.334	
R ²	0.6924	
F-value	45.044***	
Durbin-Watson	1.798	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

***=1% level of significance, **=5% level of significance, ^{NS}=Not significant

From Table 2, the R² value of 0.6924 implied that sixty-nine percent (69%) of the fluctuations in the yields of plantain was accounted for by the explanatory variables included in the model. The F-ratio of 45.044 which was significant at 1% showed that the coefficients of the explanatory variables were statistically different from zero and the Durbin Watson value of 1.798 implied the absence of autocorrelation in the model hence its goodness of fit. However, capital resources (0.034) and planting material (0.084) were statistically and positively significant at 1%. These results indicated that increase in the utilisation of the variable inputs would lead to increase in the quantity of plantain produced by smallholder farmers, thus the positive relationship. Labour (0.067) and farm size (0.017) were also positively related to rice output at 5% level of significance. These revealed that increase in labour and farm size would increase quantity of plantain produced by smallholder farmers in the area. Contrarily, cost of agrochemical (-0.084) was negatively related to plantain output at 5% level significance. This showed that increase in the use of agrochemicals led to a significant decrease in plantain output in

the area. Finally, fertilizer (-0.081) was insignificant and negatively related to plantain output in the area. This revealed the absence of fertilizer in the production of plantain in the study area.

Table 3: Estimation of Efficiency of Resource-Use and Return to Scale in Smallholder Plantain Farms Using Coefficients of Cobb-Douglas Production

Variables	Function					
	EP (bi)	TE $(\frac{output}{input})$	MPP $(bi * \frac{\bar{y}}{\bar{x}})$	MVP (mpp.py)	MFC	AEI $(\frac{mvp}{mfc})$
Capital resources (₦)	0.034	1.885	0.0641	96.15		96.15
Cost of planting material (₦)	0.084	0.234	0.0197	29.55	2000	0.0148
Labour (man-days)	0.067	3.355	0.2248	336.45	3500	0.09612
Cost of fertilizer (₦)	-0.081	1.952	-0.1581	-237.15	3500	-0.0678
Farm size (Ha)	0.017	8.722	0.1483	222.45	5000	0.0445
Cost of Agrochemicals(₦)	-0.084	2.134	-0.1792	-268.8	1500	-0.1792
Total (Return to Scale)	0.037					

Source: Field Survey, 2020

From analysis, the coefficients of Cobb-Douglas production function were used as the measure of elasticities. The sum of the elasticities of the individual production inputs were used as the measure of return to scale in the production of plantain. As such, return to scale was **0.037** which implied decreasing return to scale for smallholder plantain farmers in the study area. Also the most technical efficient factor inputs were land (8.722), labour (3.355), agrochemical (2.134), fertilizer and capital resources with the values of 1.952 and 1.885 respectively. The least technically efficient factor is planting material (0.234).

However, capital resource (96.15) was underutilized. This showed that smallholder rice farmers underutilized capital and therefore operated within stage I of the classical production function. Planting material (0.0148), labour (0.09612) and farm size (land) (0.0445) were over-utilized and the farmers therefore were in stage

III of the production function. Further analysis revealed that fertilizer (-0.0678) and agrochemical (-0.084) were extremely over-utilized as their marginal physical products were zero and this implied inefficient allocation these resources. These findings were in-line with Izekor and Alufohai (2014) whose work reported inefficiency in resource-use among southern farmers in Nigeria.

Conclusion and recommendations

Majority of the production inputs studied were significant and positively related to plantain output in the area. Smallholder plantain farmers inefficiently allocated the production inputs, though there was increasing return to scale in plantain production in the study area. Cobb-Douglas production function is strongly recommended for productivity studies as it X-rays what is obtainable in a particular study area. Smallholder plantain farmers should decrease the use of over-utilized resources and increase the use of underutilized resources to remain optimum in resource allocation and utilization in plantain production.

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